

TARA_	YYYY	MM	DD	PORT (Country)	LAT	DD	MM.MMM	LONG	DDD	MM.MMM
Start	2022	07	15	Pointe Noire (Congo)	S	04	47.040	E	011	49.521
End	2022	08	07	Banjul (Gambie)	N	13	26.418	W	016	34.477

NOTE: PLEASE COLLECT FEEDBACK ON OPERATIONS USING THIS GOOGLE FORM:

<https://forms.gle/mQ4nXHoU8q5VGkur6>

PARTICIPANTS

ROLE	NAME, Surname, Affiliation
1	CREW - Captain Baptiste Regnier
2	CREW - 1st Officer Léo Boulon
3	CREW - Engines Laurent Rogniaux
4	CREW - Deck François Aurat
5	CREW - Deck Mathieu Oriot
6	CREW - Cook Carole Pire
7	CREW - Media Guillaume Tauran
8	GUEST - Artist Irene Kopelman
9	GUEST - Observer
10	SCIENCE - A - Oceano. Engineer Charlotte Begouen Demeaux, U. Maine, USA
11	SCIENCE - B - W-Lab biogeochemistry Damaría Boussiengue, IRSEN Pointe Noire, Congo
12	SCIENCE - C - W-Lab genomics Antonella Ruggiero, SZN Naples, Italie
13	SCIENCE - D - S-Lab biogeochemistry Louis Caray—Council, Sorbonne Université, France
14	SCIENCE - E - S-Lab sorting/imaging Roland Ngomo, IRSEN Pointe Noire, Congo
15	SCIENCE - F - additional Eric Pelletier, CEA, France

SCIENTIFIC INTEREST & CAMPAIGN OBJECTIVES

(max 500 words)

4 different sampling areas with specific scientific questions are planned during this leg:

- Late Congo river plume
Effect of nutrients enrichment on plankton communities
- Equatorial seasonal upwelling
Deep rich waters upwelling – phytoplankton bloom and intense marine snow
- Guinean Dome – mesopelagic OMZ area
Cyclonic conditions generating mesopelagic OMZ waters
- Senegal upwelling zone – continental shelf upwind the upwelling area and before the Gambia river plume.

ENVIRONMENTAL CONTEXT & SAMPLING STRATEGY

(describe the stations and environments covered during the campaign, including figures as needed)

The four planned questions to address are distributed in 6 main sampling stations, as showed in Figure 1:

Figure 1: Initial Leg15 stations setup.

Station 137 targets late Congo river plume

Stations 138 – 140 targets the Equatorial seasonal upwelling

Station 141 focuses on Guinean Dome OMZ area

Station 142 will be the first of the Gambia river impact area and Senegal upwelling.

MAJOR ACHIEVEMENTS

(describe how the objectives were achieved and highlight preliminary findings and observations)

This leg started with a first station (station 137) targeting Congo river plume bloom event. This was the occasion for the science team to get familiar with operations on board, and for this purpose the station was planned on two full days to leave them time. It was a good station indeed, with no specific problem identified.

Followed a 6 days navigation to reach the next point, initiating the equator transect set of stations to study seasonal upwelling in this region.

During this time, an update is made regarding the situation of the water masses across the equator. Based on the actual data (see Figure 2), showing surface chlorophyll maximum positionned near 11°30'W we decided to move the transect accordingly.

Figure 2: Chl surface distribution across equator.

This figure shows initial planned stations (St3, 4 and 5) to study the equatorial seasonal upwelling, and the relocation based on latest data: the transect is move westward to 11° W.

We also decided to extend the range of the transect from 3° S to 3° N and to realise series of deep profiles (CTD + UVP) at 1000m every 0.5° to better characterise the water column structuration in this complex area, along with continuous TIA deployment. One full sampling station at Equator and 2 surface+DCM sampling at 3°S (station 138) and 3°N (station 150) are also planned.

Sadly, the cable showed very bad behaviour at station 138 (forming a loop on the winch leading a first cut of ~ 20 m of cable). Station 139 was worst, with discontinuities appearing along the cable, making any further use with the Rosette complete jeopardy.

Decision was taken to no longer operate the Rosette !!!

From this on, subsequent stations were redesigned to fit with our remaining functional devices and doable

operations :

- 2 TIA sensors (covering Temperature, salinity, pressure and O₂ measurements) are used for water mass profiling (with a 200m depth limitation given by the pressure sensor) using a Spectra line.
- Continuous TIA line is reduced to 8 sensors
- 2 manually operated Niskin bottles (2*12L) are deployed with the cable to sample water for SRF, DCM and epipelagic waters.
- Nets are kept operated with the cable.
- DeckNet is now only processed for surface waters

Additionally, only a very small number of filters (< 15) for Particulate Matter are available, and are reserved for the Equator station.

As a matter of consequences, stations 140 to 150 are now only consisting of a limited TIA-CTD profile down to 200m. I decided to add surface water sampling at stations 141 (1.5 °S) and 147 (1.5° N). Station 144 (Equator) is a “full” one, targeting surface, DCM (17m) and low oxygen layer (170-200m).

Figure 3: Guinean Dome station update.

Blue spot would have been the ideal location. But this update arrived while we were about to reach initial planned location (white spot) so decision was taken to keep that location.

Station 151 is localised in the eastern part of the Guinean Dome. The expected OMZ is expected somewhere between 300 and 600m. The oceanographic engineer used her magic skills to refit an O₂ sensor and the CTD from the BGT rosette to be able to explore this area (the TIA pressure sensor being limited to 200 m). And we also adapted the spare rosette frame to carry 4 * 12 L Niskin bottles with a messenger receptor on the cable to operate them (Figure 4). Tests are successfully conducted at 20m depth.

Figure 4: Rosita...

The station started with SRF waters sampling while the new CTD is sent to localise a possible OMZ area. 700 m of cable are deployed, requesting more than 1 hour of operation to be correctly rolled back on the winch (the degradation of the cable making its diameter variable, the precise rolling operation is no longer possible). An OMZ zone is indeed identified between 420 and 500 m deep. The next day, our Rosita (the mini-Rosette) is sent to the OMZ. Sadly, the cable damages prevent the messenger to reach Rosita, and the bottles are upped open. During the rolling back, new damages on the cable are detected, and decision is made to no longer try to use it

on long distances. Adios OMZ...

Meanwhile, Sargassum patches are spotted (see Figure 5), and at least can we sample some of them.

Figure 5: Sargassum patch

Last station, 152, is located on the continental shelf in Gambian waters (see station 0 on Figure 6), close to the coast, with 19 m depth. TIA profile shows an homogeneous mixed layer, so only surface is sampled.

Figure 6: Planned stations to study Senegal upwelling and Gambia river influence.

SUMMARY OF ACTIVITIES

(Provide an overview of sampling activities on every day of the Campaign, indicating the number of deployments done for each type of event)

Station ###	Date, start YYYY-MM-DD	Latitude, start N dd.dddddd	Longitude, start E ddd.dddddd	UDW - Aerosols	UDW - Biogeochemistry	BGC - CAST - 0-1000	SML	SRF - PUMP	SRF - NET - WPII 20	SRF - NET - WPII 200	SRF - NET - Manta 330	EPI - CAST - 0-200	EPI - NET - WPII 20	EPI - NET - WPII 200	EPI - Régent 680	MESO - CAST - 0-1000	CAST - Trace Metals	VMP - Profile	TIA - Towed Array	BowPole	hTSRB
137	2022-07-18	S 05	E 005					1	2	1	1	2	1	1	2	2		2		1	
138	2022-07-25	S 03	W 011.5					1	1	1						1				1	
139	2022-07-27	S 02.5	W 011.5													1					
140	2022-07-26	S 02	W 011.5													1					
141	2022-07-26	S 01.5	W 011.5					1	1	1										1	
142	2022-07-26	S 01	W 011.5													1			1		
143	2022-07-27	S 00.5	W 011.4													1					
144	2022-07-28	S 00	W 011.5					1	1	1	1		1	1	2	1		2		1	
145	2022-07-29	N 00.5	W 011.5									1									
146	2022-07-30	N 01	W 011.5									1									
147	2022-07-30	N 01.5	W 011.5					1	1	1		1								1	
148	2022-07-30	N 02	W 011.5									1									
149	2022-07-31	N 02.5	W 011.5									1									
150	2022-07-31	N 03	W 012					1	1	1		1								1	
151	2022-08-03	N 08	W 017.9					1					1	1	1			2			
152	2022-08-07	N 13.1	W 017					1	1	1	1	1				1				1	

STATION PLAN

Station Label: 137

Station Title: Late Congo river Plume

(Fill the Table as a plan before the station and correct it after the station using the Event Logsheets)

Time UTC	Duration	Event	Depth(s)	Comment	A	B	C	D	E	F
06:00	30'	Rosette #1	600	SRF Z0 = 4m	x					x
06:45		A20 pump		SRF Z0 = 0m		x	x	x	x	
06:55	30'	VMP250	200		x					x
07:25	30'	VMP250	200		x					x
07:55	10'	WP11-200 horizontal	5		x			x	x	x
08:10	10'	WP11-20 horizontal	5		x			x	x	x
09:20	15'	Rosette #2	4	SRF Z0 = 4m (for BGC)						x
11:05	60'	Manta	SRF		x				x	x
12:30	20'	WP11-200 vertical	200	Flow-meter forgotten	x			x	x	x
13:00	20'	Rosette #3	28	DCM Z2 = 28m omics						
14:00	20'	Rosette #4	28	DCM Z2 = 28m decknet						
14:50	20'	WP11-20 vertical	200		x			x	x	x
15:30	20'	Regent 680	200		x			x	x	x
16:30	15'	Bow pole			x					x
05:50	60'	Rosette #5	600	MESO Z6 = 400m						
07:40	60'	Rosette #6	600	MESO Z6 = 400m						
09:15	30'	WP11 20 vertical	200		x			x	x	x
10:00	30'	Rosette #7	200	MESO Z4 = 200m						
12:00	30'	Rosette #8	200	MESO Z4 = 200m						
16:00	15'	Regent 680	200		x			x	x	x

STATION PLAN

Station Label: 138

Station Title: South of Equatorial seasonal upwelling - 3° S

(Fill the Table as a plan before the station and correct it after the station using the Event Logsheets)

Time UTC	Duration	Event	Depth(s)	Comment	A	B	C	D	E	F
11:45	105'	Rosette #1	1000	Z0 = 3-5 m	x		x	x		x
12:15	20'	A20 pump	5	Z0 = 3-5 m	x	x			x	x
13:45	15'	WP11-20+200 horizontal	5	Z0 = 3-5 m	x			x	x	x
14:30	10'	Bow Pole	SRF		x					x

STATION PLAN

Station Label: 139

Station Title: South of Equatorial seasonal upwelling - 2.5° S

(Fill the Table as a plan before the station and correct it after the station using the Event Logsheets)

Time UTC	Duration	Event	Depth(s)	Comment	A	B	C	D	E	F
21:30	120'	Rosette #1	1000		x					x

STATION PLAN

Station Label: 140

Station Title: South of Equatorial seasonal upwelling - 2° S

(Fill the Table as a plan before the station and correct it after the station using the Event Logsheets)

Time UTC	Duration	Event	Depth(s)	Comment	A	B	C	D	E	F
6:00	75'	Rosette #1	1000	CTD + UVP profile only	x					x

Station Label: 141

Station Title: South of Equatorial seasonal upwelling - 1.5° S

(Fill the Table as a plan before the station and correct it after the station using the Event Logsheets)

Time UTC	Duration	Event	Depth(s)	Comment	A	B	C	D	E	F
13:20	20'	A20 pump		Z0 = 3 m		x	x	x	x	
14:13	10'	Niskin (*2)	3	Z0 = 3-5 m	x					x
14:44	10'	WPII 20+200µm horizontal	3	Z0 = 3-5 m						
14:44	10'	Niskin (*2)	3	Z0 = 3-5 m	x					x
15:15	25'	TIA - CTD	200		x					x
16:05	5'	Bow pole			x					x

Station Label: 142

Station Title: South of Equatorial seasonal upwelling - 1° S

(Fill the Table as a plan before the station and correct it after the station using the Event Logsheets)

Time UTC	Duration	Event	Depth(s)	Comment	A	B	C	D	E	F
20:50	34 h	TIA on route		On until 20220728	X					x
21:05	30'	TIA - CTD	200		x					x

Station Label: 143

Station Title: South of Equatorial seasonal upwelling - 0.5° S

(Fill the Table as a plan before the station and correct it after the station using the Event Logsheets)

Time UTC	Duration	Event	Depth(s)	Comment	A	B	C	D	E	F
06:00	25'	TIA - CTD	200		x					x

STATION PLAN

Station Label: 144

Station Title: Equatorial seasonal upwelling

(Fill the Table as a plan before the station and correct it after the station using the Event Logsheets)

Time UTC	Duration	Event	Depth(s)	Comment	A	B	C	D	E	F
07:00	60'	TIA - CTD	200		x					x
06:30		A20 pump		SRF Z0 = 3 m		x	x	x	x	
06:55	30'	VMP250	200		x					x
07:25	30'	VMP250	200		x					x
07:55	10'	WPII-200 horizontal	5		x			x	x	x
08:10	10'	WPII-20 horizontal	5		x			x	x	x
11:05	60'	Manta	SRF		x				x	x
12:30	20'	WPII-200 vertical	200		x			x	x	x
13:00	20'	Niskins (*2)	18	DCM Z2 = 18 m						
14:00	20'	Niskins (*2)	88	DCM Z2 = 18 m						
14:50	20'	WPII-20 vertical	200		x			x	x	x
15:30	20'	Regent 680	200		x			x	x	x
16:30	15'	Bow pole			x					x
05:50	60'	Niskins (*2)	600	DCM Z2 = 18 m						
07:40	60'	Niskins (*2)	600	DCM Z2 = 18 m						
09:15	30'	WPII 20 vertical	200		x			x	x	x
10:00	30'	Niskins (*2)	200	DCM Z2 = 18 m	x		x	x		x
12:00	30'	Niskins (*2)	200	DCM Z2 = 18 m	x	x			x	x
16:00	15'	Regent 680	200		x			x	x	x

STATION PLAN

Station Label: 145

Station Title: North of Equatorial seasonal upwelling - 0.5° N

(Fill the Table as a plan before the station and correct it after the station using the Event Logsheets)

Time UTC	Duration	Event	Depth(s)	Comment	A	B	C	D	E	F
20:30	30'	TIA as CTD	200		x					x

STATION PLAN

Station Label: 146

Station Title: North of Equatorial seasonal upwelling - 1° N

(Fill the Table as a plan before the station and correct it after the station using the Event Logsheets)

Time UTC	Duration	Event	Depth(s)	Comment	A	B	C	D	E	F
07:00	20'	TIA as CTD	200		x					x

Station Label: 147

Station Title: North of Equatorial seasonal upwelling - 1.5° N

(Fill the Table as a plan before the station and correct it after the station using the Event Logsheets)

Time UTC	Duration	Event	Depth(s)	Comment	A	B	C	D	E	F
13:40	25'	TIA - CTD	200		x					x
13:50	20'	A20 pump		Z0 = 3 m		x	x	x	x	
14:20	5'	Niskin (*2)	3	Z0 = 3-5 m	x	x	x			x
14:25	5'	Niskin (*2)	3	Z0 = 3-5 m	x			x	x	x
14:37	15'	WPII 20+200µm horizontal	3	Z0 = 3-5 m				x	x	
15:15	5'	Bow pole			x					x

Station Label: 148

Station Title: North of Equatorial seasonal upwelling - 2° N

(Fill the Table as a plan before the station and correct it after the station using the Event Logsheets)

Time UTC	Duration	Event	Depth(s)	Comment	A	B	C	D	E	F
20:00	20'	TIA as CTD	200		x					x

Station Label: 149

Station Title: North of Equatorial seasonal upwelling - 2.5° N

(Fill the Table as a plan before the station and correct it after the station using the Event Logsheets)

Time UTC	Duration	Event	Depth(s)	Comment	A	B	C	D	E	F
06:00	30'	TIA as CTD	200		x					x

STATION PLAN

Station Label: 150

Station Title: North of Equatorial seasonal upwelling - 3° N

(Fill the Table as a plan before the station and correct it after the station using the Event Logsheets)

Time UTC	Duration	Event	Depth(s)	Comment	A	B	C	D	E	F
13:00	30'	TIA as CTD	200		x					x
13:10	20'	A20 pump		SRF Z0 = 3 m		x	x	x	x	
13:45	10'	Niskin (*2)	3	Z0 = 3-5 m	x					x
14:00	10'	WPII 20+200µm horizontal	3	Z0 = 3-5 m						
14:30	10'	Niskin (*2)	3	Z0 = 3-5 m	x					x
14:45	5'	Bow Pole			X					x

STATION PLAN

Station Label: 151

Station Title: Guinean dome

(Fill the Table as a plan before the station and correct it after the station using the Event Logsheets)

Time UTC	Duration	Event	Depth(s)	Comment	A	B	C	D	E	F
14:00	60'	CTD #1	700		x					x
14:20	20'	A20 pump		SRF Z0 = 3 m		x	x	x	x	
16:00	10'	Rosita #2	3	SRF 4 * 12 L Z0 = 3 m	x					x
17:15	20'	Regent 680	200		x			x	x	x
07:30	15'	Regent 680	200		x			x	x	x
08:00	15'	TIA as CTD	200							
10:15	15'	Rosita #2	50	DCM Z2 = 50 m	x					x
10:30	15'	Rosita #3	50	DCM Z2 = 50 m	x					x
10:50	10'	WP11-200 vertical	200		x			x	x	x
12:00	15'	Rosita #4	50	DCM Z2 = 50 m	x					x
13:50	20'	WP11-20 vertical	200		x			x	x	x
15:00	30'	VMP250	200		x					x
15:20	30'	VMP250	200		x					x
16:50	10'	WP11-20+200 horizontal	5		x			x	x	x
	10'	Sargasses sampling	SRF		x		x			x

INVENTORY OF SAMPLES COLLECTED DURING THE CAMPAIGN

(fill the table based on the sample IDs on the logsheets)

	Storage T°C	RT+10 B-Box	RT+10 G-box	RT+10 XXL	FRG+ 4 W- box-S	FRG+ 4 W- box-M	FRG+ 4 W- box-L	FRZ-20 W-box- S	FRZ-20 W-box- M	FRZ-20 W-box- L	LN-80 Dewar #1	LN-80 Dewar #2	LN-80 Dewar #3
Protocol	Container type												
DGAS	ExeV-12mL						28						
DIC13	200-mL-Bottle		0										
DICTA	500-mL-bottle		14										
DO18	AmberV-40mL			0									
NUT-1	20mLCryoV						13						
SAL	125-mL Bottle			3									
DINO	60-mL-Bottle						22						
HG-M	125-mL Bottle			14									
HG-T	40-mL-Bottle			0									
MTE-T	60-mL-Bottle			0									
MTE-F	60-mL-Bottle			0									
MTE-BP	125-mL-Bottle			7									
MB320	4-mL-Vial							23					
MB023	4-mL-Vial							23					
MB<02	50-mL-falcon								23				
eDNA	sterivex								24				
NP550	20-mL-vial								14				
NP045	4-mL-Vial							14					
HG	Zip-lock	1											
PM	Zip-lock	7											
S320	5-mL-cryotube										31		
S023	5-mL-cryotube										31		
S<02	5-mL-cryotube							29					
P320	5-mL-cryotube										14		
P023	5-mL-cryotube										14		
HP	2-mL-cryotube											31	
SG	5-mL-cryotube										28		
FC	2-mL-cryotube												90
HC	2-mL-cryotube											42	
SEM	petri-slide	14											
FM20	50-mL-falcon				3								
E20	15-mL-falcon								3				
S20	5-mL-cryotube										11		

